

AN EXPERIMENTAL AND THEORETICAL STUDY OF STRESSES IN LAMINATED BEAMS

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ABSTRACT

A new theory for bending of laminated beams has been developed. Calculated values of interlaminar shear and bending stresses compare favourably with photoelastic measurements on model beams.

The photoelastic model consists of three layers, an anisotropic, non-transparent layer sandwiched between two isotropic, transparent layers of photoelastic material. The beam is simply supported and loaded by a small cylindrical roller over a narrow band of its upper edge, resulting in high contact stresses at the concentrated loading.

The calculations are based on the exact elastic theory in conjunction with an approximate method of evaluating the contact stresses using Boussinesq and Hertz contact theory. A computer program has been developed for evaluating the stresses at any position in the beam. Beam dimensions, layer thicknesses, anisotropies and loading conditions can be varied.

INTRODUCTION

Laminated structures exhibit properties considerably different from those of single-layer structures because of the relatively low interlaminar shear modulus in composites. The theories based on the assumption of non deformable normals, which are found to be sufficiently accurate and acceptable for single-layer, isotropic structures, are often quite unacceptable for laminated, anisotropic structures.¹⁻⁷

Many approximate analysis methods have been proposed^{4, 6-13}, however the accuracy of such analyses can only be determined by comparison with a solution obtained from the exact theory of elasticity or with experimental results. Exact solutions are only available for simple loading and boundary conditions^{1-3, 5, 14} and few experimental studies exist¹⁵⁻¹⁸. In this paper the exact elastic theory is used to determine the stress distribution in a laminated beam under three-point loading and an approximate theory is developed to find the stress concentration close to loading points. The results from both methods are compared with photoelastic measurements of stresses in a three-layer beam and the applicability and limitations of each method are discussed.

THEORETICAL SOLUTION FOR BENDING - EXACT BEAM THEORY

Exact solutions for simply supported composite beams under various loading conditions have previously been derived^{1, 2, 5}. A summary of the relevant theory² is included here as a precursor to the approximate theory developed in the next section.

A simply supported, laminated beam with n layers is shown in Fig. 1. A load $P_0 \sin \frac{n\pi x}{l}$ is applied to the top surface of the beam, where P_0 is a known constant and n an integer. Taking the x axis to be along the central plane of the

i^{th} layer under consideration, the stresses in that layer are assumed to take the form

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_x^{(i)} &= f_i''(z) \sin \frac{n\pi x}{l} \\ \sigma_z^{(i)} &= -\frac{n^2 \pi^2}{l^2} f_i(z) \sin \frac{n\pi x}{l} \\ \tau_{xz}^{(i)} &= -\frac{n\pi}{l} f_i'(z) \cos \frac{n\pi x}{l}\end{aligned}\quad (2.1)$$

Fig. 1

where $f_i^i(z)$ is an unknown function of z .

The stresses clearly satisfy the end conditions $\sigma_x = \sigma_z = 0$ of the beam and can be shown to satisfy the equilibrium equations provided the weight of the beam is neglected.

Substituting (2-1) and the stress-strain equations for an anisotropic material into the compatibility equation yields an ordinary differential equation in f_i as follows:

$$R_{11}^{(i)} f_i'''' - [R_{55}^{(i)} + 2R_{13}^{(i)}] \lambda^2 f_i'' + R_{33}^{(i)} \lambda^4 f_i = 0 \quad (2.2)$$

where $\lambda = n\pi/l$ and R_{11} etc. are material constants. The general solution of 2.2 as given in ref. 5 is

$$f_i(z) = \sum_{j=1}^4 A_j^{(i)} \exp(m_j^{(i)} \cdot z) \quad 2.3$$

$$m_j^{(i)} = \pm \lambda \left(\frac{a_i + b_i}{c_i} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad j = 1, 2 \quad 2.4$$

$$m_j^{(i)} = \pm \lambda \left(\frac{a_i - b_i}{c_i} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad j = 3, 4$$

$$a_i = R_{55}^{(i)} + 2R_{13}^{(i)}$$

$$b_i = (a_i^2 - 4R_{11}^{(i)} R_{33}^{(i)})^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad 2.5$$

$$c_i = 2R_{11}^{(i)}$$

where A_j represents four unknown constants for the i^{th} layer.

The roots of equation 2.2 are real and equal for an isotropic layer, but may be real or complex in an anisotropic layer depending on the degree of anisotropy.

The solution for $f_i(z)$ is substituted into equations 2.1 to obtain the stresses in terms of the unknown constants A_j . Displacements can also be obtained by integration. For a laminated beam with n layers there will be $4n$ unknown constants which are determined by considering continuity and equilibrium conditions between layers and boundary conditions on the upper and lower surfaces.

THEORETICAL SOLUTION FOR A CONCENTRATED LOAD - COMBINED CONTACT/BEAM THEORY

The upper layer of the laminated beam is isotropic and a concentrated load P is applied on the top surface through a roller, midway between the supports. The solution to this problem can be found by combining the theory of the previous section with Hertzian contact theory to give stresses directly below the concentrated load as follows.

Firstly, assume that the concentrated load acts on a semi-infinite plane as shown in Fig. 2. Plane Hertzian contact theory gives a parabolic load distribution q on the upper surface and allows the stresses directly below this load to be calculated in terms of the half width b , the roller radius and the force P .

Fig. 2

Consider a strip, taken from the semi-infinite plane, geometrically equivalent to the upper isotropic layer of the beam. Line 2-3 is in the interface of the upper and adjacent layers. The contact stresses within this strip are denoted by S_A and the stress distribution along the boundaries 1-2, 2-3, and 3-4 by $(S_A)_b$.

Furthermore, let the stress distribution along the equivalent boundaries, calculated using the exact beam theory of the previous section, be $(S_B)_b$. This calculation requires a series loading of the upper surface i.e.

$\sum p_n \sin \frac{n\pi x}{l}$. Normally 15 terms or more are needed to model the concentrated load

allowing convergence of the stresses on the interface. In general $(S_A)_b \neq (S_B)_b$.

The next stage is to solve the boundary problem shown in Fig. 3, where the boundary forces on 1-2-3-4 are taken as the difference $(S_B)_b - (S_A)_b$ and the surface is free of load.

Fig. 3

the strip denoted by S_C . Finally, the stress condition $S_C + S_C$ is the required stress distribution in the upper layer of the beam, including the effects of the stress concentration. This is clearly the case as the strip size and material is the same as the upper layer of the beam, a concentrated load P acts on the upper surface, and the stresses along the boundaries 1-2, 2-3, 3-4 are the same as those obtained from the exact theory of the previous section.

A stress function method has been used to solve the boundary problem, incorporating point matching of stresses at 26 selected points along the boundary.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

1. Manufacture of a 3 Layer Beam

A three-layer beam was manufactured, comprising an upper and a lower isotropic layer and a central, anisotropic layer. Each layer is $\frac{1}{4}$ in (6.35 mm) in both width and depth and 6 in (152.4 mm) in length, as shown in Fig. 4. The isotropic layers were machined from $\frac{1}{4}$ in Araldite, cast in a vertical plate mould. The anisotropic layer was cut from $\frac{1}{4}$ in thick filament wound plate of Crystic 272 Polyester resin/E glass continuous filament laminate. This strip was cut with the main fibre direction lying along the beam axis.

Fig. 4

All layers were machined flat, dried and assembled using slow curing Araldite adhesive, curing at room temperature for 24 hours. Optimum pressure on the joints had to be determined to give an even adhesive thickness and minimise shrinkage stresses. With care, initial stresses were kept below a fringe order of 0.3.

2. Loading Conditions and Photoelastic Measurements

Photoelastic measurements of the initial fringe pattern were taken to determine the shrinkage stresses arising during manufacture of the beam. The beam was then loaded under three-point bending conditions with $\frac{1}{4}$ in diameter steel outer support pins at a span of 4 in. A dead-weight load equivalent to 26.1 N/mm of beam width was applied through the central loading pin nominally $\frac{1}{4}$ in, in diameter (see Fig. 4). Fringe orders and isoclinic angles were measured in the upper and lower isotropic layers, down the centre line of the beam (i.e. below the loading pin) and along the upper and lower interfaces between layers.

Material fringe values for the isotropic layers were determined by loading the beam under four point bending and assuming an equivalent flexural rigidity for the three-layer beam. Based on these values and correcting for initial stress, stress differences down the centre line and interfacial shear stresses were calculated.

RESULTS

The experimental and theoretical results are shown in Figs. 5 and 6. Fig. 5 shows the normalised, direct stress difference down the centre line for the upper and lower isotropic layers. z is the distance below the central loading point. The normalising stress is taken as the maximum bending stress (in the lower surface, under the load) which would occur in a fully isotropic beam of the same dimensions under the same loading. In the upper layer experimental results are compared with theoretical results from both the exact beam theory and the combined theory. In the lower layer experimental results are compared with the exact theory alone.

Fig. 6 shows the normalised shear stress distribution (a) along the upper interface i.e. between the upper and middle layers and (b) along the lower interface i.e. between the middle and lower layers. The stresses are plotted as a function of position x/l where x is the distance from a point directly below the central load and l is the span of the beam. In this case the normalising stress is taken as the average shear stress occurring in an isotropic beam of the same dimensions under the same loading. Experimental results are compared with theoretical results as for the bending stresses.

Fig. 5 - Normalised direct stress difference down the beam centre line for the upper and lower isotropic layers.

Fig. 6 - Normalised shear stress along (a) the upper interface and (b) the lower interface against distance, x/l from a point directly below the central load.

DISCUSSION

The results given by the exact beam theory with 20 loading terms agree well with both the measured bending stresses in the lower layer and the interfacial shear stresses along the lower interface. Although more terms are generally required to represent a concentrated loading accurately (200 in our case), increasing the number of terms has no appreciable effect on the stress distribution remote from the contact point. Thus the exact beam theory with a limited number of terms is adequate for predicting bending and shear stress distributions away from contact loading points and support reactions.

Fig. 5 clearly shows that this theory is inadequate for predicting the effects of the contact force on the bending stress distribution in the upper layer, particularly in a region close to this point, where very large compressive stresses occur. Fig. 6(a) also shows that, although the exact beam theory predicts the existence of the peak in the shear stress distribution along the upper interface, the magnitude of this peak is overestimated. As such peaks in interfacial shear stress may give rise to laminate failure, accurate prediction of their magnitude is important, particularly where interfaces lie close to the loading point. The limitations of the exact theory are a result of the inaccurate modelling of the concentrated parabolic load distribution. The combined contact/beam theory predicts both the bending and shear stress distributions in the upper layer. Agreement with the shear stress peak is excellent.

The numerical solution of the exact beam theory is straight forward and flexible. Beam dimensions, number of layers and thicknesses, anisotropies and loading conditions can all be varied. A computer program has been developed for this purpose. The combined contact/beam theory applies only to the layer in contact with the load. Currently this is limited to an isotropic layer, although future modifications will allow extension to contact on anisotropic layers. Furthermore, the theory does not allow for contact influence below the top layer which will undoubtedly be the case for thin layers. Finally it should be emphasised that the combined theory is only an approximate solution with accuracy depending on the number of boundary matching points selected for the solution.

CONCLUSIONS

A new approximate theory combining Hertzian contact theory with an exact elastic theory has been developed for calculating stresses in laminated beams at positions close to load contact points. The theory agrees well with photoelastic measurements of bending stresses and interlaminar shear stresses. At positions where the influence of contact is minimal, the exact elastic theory on its own has been shown to be adequate. For this theory a flexible computer program has been written, allowing beam and loading conditions to be varied. Experimental techniques have been developed for manufacturing layered beams with low initial stresses for photoelastic analysis. The experimental results have been shown to be important in assessing the applicability of the particular theories.

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